

Indicators for the NOSCI's establishment **CHECKLIST**

How to use this document

The setting up of National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI) cannot be taken as a linear process. There is no “one solution fits all”, country/community-specific considerations must be taken into account.

Nascent efforts in South East Europe have already chosen different pathways for their formulation according to different partner and country profiles and needs. These efforts might operate as task forces, consortia, national projects, professional associations or legal entities. In any case, the use of monitoring indicators already at early stages will help the assessment of status, the monitoring of the progress and will assist to adapt the workflow of the NOSCI implementation to the region.

Here, we propose an indicative set of metrics that may be used for the assessment of the status and progress of the NOSCI in the region. The proposed indicators are in line with the European Open Science Cloud Readiness Indicators and may be used as a guide to complement the establishment and operation of a NOSCI. The framework should be both, agile and expandable to successfully address any countries-specific needs.

The metrics are categorized in four distinct categories:

- The first category: NOSCI organisation is focused on organisational, administrative and legal aspects of the NOSCI.
- The second category: Infrastructure is focused on the core infrastructure aspects: the infrastructure itself and its operations.
- The third category: Training and Skills assesses the nature and spread of the training activities within the NOSCI community.
- The fourth category: Sustainability and international collaboration is focused on financial issues related to long-term sustainability of the NOSCI, as well as its relationship with international organisations, specifically in terms of sustainability at European level.

All four main categories have been accompanied by sub-categories of indicators that provided a higher granularity.

Glossary

AAI	Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Core	A set of services providing the means to discover, share, access and re-use data and services.
EOSC-Exchange	A set of services storing and exploiting FAIR data and encouraging its reuse.
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FitSM	FitSM is a lightweight standard for IT service management. It brings order and traceability with simple, practical support and provides a common conceptual and process model setting out realistic requirements.
NOSCI	National Open Science Cloud Initiative
OS	Open Science
OSC	Open Science Cloud

1. Organisation of the NOSCI

Set-up metrics

NOSCI is established

Yes No

NOSCI initiating body

Name:

Type:

NOSCI set-up document

URL:

Description:

NOSCI mandate duration

Date:

NOSCI set-up event carried out [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

Date:

Type of event: [Conference, Workshop, Online meeting, Other]

Organisational metrics

Form of the NOSCI:

Task force

Consortium

- National programme
- Professional association
- Standalone organisation
- Legal entity
- Other

Is there a Coordination body established?

Yes No

Nomination of the representative

Name:

Description:

Date:

NOSCI endorsement at the national level

Entity providing endorsement:

Type of endorsement:

- Law
- Decree
- Letter of Support
- Other [Please describe]

Document: [URL]

Date:

Membership

Number of participating organisations:

Type and number of organisations:

Academic:

Research:

Technology provider:

Service provider:

Funding bodies:

Non-profit:

Commercial:

Other organisations:

Are there any organisations with observer status?

Yes No

Please specify:

NOSCI Documents

National / Institutional policies on Open Science exist [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

Content:

URL:

Date of latest update:

Strategic roadmap on Open Science exists [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Date of latest update:

National Open Science Cloud Strategy document exists [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Date of latest update:

2. Infrastructure & Services

Infrastructure metrics

Type of infrastructures:

National Research infrastructures (including ESFRIs)

Yes No

Number:

Please answer for each of infrastructure

Access policies are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Privacy policies are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Security policies are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Terms of Use are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

National e-infrastructures (HPC, Cloud etc.)

Yes No

Number:

Please answer for each of infrastructure

Access policies are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Privacy policies are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Security policies are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Terms of Use are in place [If "Yes", please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Other Research Infrastructures

Yes No

Number:

Please answer for each of infrastructure

Name:

Description:

Access policies are in place [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Privacy policies are in place [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Security policies are in place [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Terms of Use are in place [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Services metrics

Total number of services offered:

Number of onboarded services:

Number of services per type of service:

Generic

Thematic.....

Operational.....

List services offered in **EOSC-Exchange**:

.....

List services integrated with **EOSC-Core**:

.....

Number of services following IT Service Management processes (FITSM or equivalent) per type of service:

- Generic
- Thematic
- Operational.....

Number of FAIR-enabling services per type of service:

- Generic
- Thematic
- Operational.....

 Operational metrics

National (regional) registry or other federation mechanisms for resources (computing, data, storage) are in place/planned [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

Date of Establishment:

National Open Science portal exists [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

National Open Science helpdesk exists [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

National Open Science service monitoring exists [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

URL:

National AAI federation availability

Yes No

URL:

3. Training & Skills

Community Metrics

National/regional curricula are in place/planned [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

Description:

Basic training is available for researchers & research support staff (e.g., National Competence centers) [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

Description:

Number of trained people per year and thematic coverage

[Number, Thematic coverage]

Number of training material and thematic coverage

[Number, Thematic coverage]

4. Sustainability and international collaboration

Funding Metrics

National Fund for OS/OSC is in place/ planned [If yes, please specify]

Yes No

Name:

URL:

If National fund for OSC projects exist, specify per project

Type: Infrastructure Software Services Data Skills

Number:

Duration:

Participation in International and European OSC Projects

Yes No

If international and European OSC projects exist, specify per project

Type: Infrastructure Software Services Data Skills
 NOSCI operation

Number:

Duration:

Sustainability plan is in place / planned

Yes No

Description:

Metrics concerning membership in international bodies / fora

EOSC Association participation

Yes No

Pan-European initiatives participation related to EOSC (EOSC Pillars) [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

Name:

Description:

Other [If “Yes”, please specify]

Yes No

Name:

Description: